

Resistance of elite rice strains and varieties to bacterial blight (BB)

S.S. Malik, Haryana Agricultural University (HAU), Rice Research Station, Kaul (Kurukshetra), India

One hundred thirty-two strains of rice were evaluated for resistance to BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* at HAU Regional Research Station, Uchahi Karnal, during the 1983 and 1984 wet seasons (Jul-Oct).

Rice plants were inoculated at maximum tillering stage by cutting 5 cm of the upper leaf portion with a sickle dipped in a single-isolate inoculum. The inoculum was prepared by soaking small pieces of naturally infected leaves in water for 20 min.

Disease reactions were scored 15 d after inoculation (*Standard evaluation system for rice*). Strains showing reaction 1-3 were rated resistant (R); 5, moderately resistant (MR); and 7-9, susceptible (S).

Among 30 short-duration strains tested, 7 were R, 13 MR, and 10 S (see table). Among 50 medium-duration strains, 15 were R, 15 MR, and 20 S. Among 52 scented strains, 11 were R, 12 MR, and 29 S.

Short- and medium-duration TKM6, BJI, IET4141, UPRB31, and DV85 have been used as BB resistance donors. In the scented group, resistance to BB has not been developed. □

Elite rice strains showing resistance and moderate resistance to BB in 1983-84. Kurukshetra, India.

Resistant (1-3)	Moderately resistant (5)
<i>Short duration</i>	
HAUK6-88-1	HKR4
HAUK8-75-1-3	HAUK8-145-1
HAU28-3643-1	HAUK9-176-1
PAU154-453-3	HKR21
IR9763-11-2-2-3	HAU47-3888-3
MRC630-303	HAU118-278
325/UNN-5-1	HAU6-63-1
	IR36
	IR9828-91-2-3
	IR313429-196-1
	C1322-28
	PR103
	Pal 579
<i>Medium duration</i>	
HKR109	HKR108
HAUK6-0-2-1	HKR110
HAUK6-0-3-2	HAUK8-45-3-2
HAUK7-176-3-2	HAUK10-0-19
HAUK7-217-1	HAUK10-189-1
HAUK8-0-23-3	HAUK10-221-1
HAUK8-204-1	HAUK102
HAUK9-98-2-2-1	HAUK23A-10
HAUK10-37-2	HAUK23A-67
HAUK10-189-2	HAUK27-10-2
HAUK10-221-2	HAUK28-22-1
HAUK10-228-2	HAUK30-0-1
HAUK8-10-15-2	HAU118-154
IRON81-169	RP5121-173-1-8
IRON81-171	RP2136-43-2
<i>Scented</i>	
HKR222	HKR221
HAUKIO-0-3-12	T3 dw. mutant
HAUK10-0-37-5	HAUK23c-95
HAUK10-221-1-7-1	HAUK10-0-25
HAUK10-184-1-5-1	HAUK10-37-3
HAUK10-211-1-5	HAUK12-72-1-3-1
HAUK12-20-4-2	HAUK33-4-2
HAUK12-52-4-2	HAUK34-9-2
HAUK12-64-4-1-1	HAUK35-11-5
HAUK23B-39	HAU36A-67-1
HAUK12-88-1	HAUK3613-1-1
	HAUK36F-14-1

moisture content was estimated from healthy panicles. Entries with 0% infestation = highly resistant (HR), 1-20% = resistant (R), 21-40% = moderately resistant (MR), 41-60% = moderately susceptible (MS), 61-80% = susceptible (S), and 81-100% = highly susceptible (HS).

All Rayada entries showed resistance and high yield potential (see table). □

Ufra infestation and yield of selected deep water rice entries, DWR Project, Joydebpur, Bangladesh.

Entry	Ufra infestation (%)	Reaction	Yield (t/ha)
Rayada 16-06	1	R	4.5
Rayada 16-08	1	R	4.0
Rayada 16-09	1	R	4.0
Rayada 16-02	2	R	5.0
Rayada 16-03	2	R	4.7
Rayada 16-013	2	R	4.1
Rayada 16-07	4	R	4.1
Rayada 16-011	4	R	4.4
Rayada 16-05	11	R	4.3
CNL-319	23	MR	3.6
BR306-B-3-2	31	MR	3.6
BR308-B-2-2	37	MR	2.6
Bazail65	35	MR	1.9
Dalkatra	40	MR	2.8
Choruamotor	44	MR	2.9
Gowai 50/9	44	MR	2.4
Karkati 161	44	MR	1.6
BR308-B-2-9/A	54	MR	2.4
Hassi Amon (check)	95	HS	0.9
Habiganj Amon I (check)	93	HS	0.6

Performance of medium-duration IRRI lines at Tamil Nadu

M. Subramanian, V. Sivasubramanian, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu; and G.S. Khush, IRRI

Forty-five IRRI lines were evaluated during 1984 thaladi season (Sep-Oct to Jan-Feb) with medium-duration check CO 43.

Entries were raised in trial plots. At 32 d, they were planted 2-3 to a hill, spaced 20 cm between rows and 10 cm

Source of ufra-resistant deep water rice

M.L. Rahman, DWR Project, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Gazipur, Bangladesh

In a series of trials during the 1981-85 growing seasons, 1,358 deep water rice entries were screened in pots or deep water tanks (DWT) for ufra nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* resistance. In the

pot trials, 3- and 4-wk-old entries were inoculated artificially by releasing 100 active nematodes per seedling in 8-10 cm water. On the basis of infestation percentage and number of nematodes per plant, 18 entries were found resistant or moderately resistant to ufra.

Those entries were retested in deep water tanks. Each entry was sown in three 1- × 1-m plots and inoculated.

At harvest, panicles were evaluated as diseased or healthy. Yield at 14%